

Minutes of the 54th Experimenters' Meeting

The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 22nd January 2015

(This document was finalised on 30th April 2015)

Present:

(CG) Dr Catherine Gaffard⁴
(CJW) Dr Chris Walden^{3,6}
(DAH) Dr David Hooper^{5,6} Secretary
(EGN) Dr Emily Norton⁷
(GAP) Dr Graham Parton^{2,6}
(GM) Mr Graeme Marlton⁸
(GV) Prof Geraint Vaughan⁷ Chair
(HMAR) Dr Hugo Ricketts⁷
(LD) Mr Les Dean^{1,5}
(LJD) Mrs Lizzy Dyson⁴
(ZL) Dr Zhihong Li⁴

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³Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research

⁴Met Office

⁵NERC MST Radar Facility

⁶Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁷University of Manchester

⁸University of Reading

Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMF Atmospheric Measurement Facility (formerly FGAM)
BLWP Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
DPW David Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
GPS Global Positioning System
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
NLC Noctilucent Cloud
Mbps megabits per second
PC Personal Computer
PCA BLWP data acquisition PC
PCT BLWP data processing PC
PTU pressure, temperature, and humidity
SAOZ Système d'Analyse par Observation Zénithale
S/N Signal-to-noise ratio
TX Transmitter
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

DAH spotted a small error in the 2nd paragraph of section 4a on page 5: “GV emphasised that files containing false positive precipitation readings, e.g. for 10th May 2014, should be removed from the BADC.” This should have referred to 30th May 2014.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK [Dirk Klugmann - former manager of the Met Office's Upper Air Sensing Team] to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he had been unable to meet any of the relevant people when he had visited the Met Office following the previous Experimenters' meeting. Some of these people were not available and others had moved on to other areas of responsibility. However, he aimed to continue with this action.

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

DAH will give an update on this work in section 6f.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

No time has been devoted to the four action items above - 47.2.1, 47.2.2, 47.3.2, and 51.4.1 - since the last meeting.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

LJD reported that she would check internally to see if the Met Office would allow this.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.1 JMT [Jim Trice - Met Office's wind-profiler network manager at the time of 53rd meeting] and LJD to report at the next meeting on the effects of the recent renovation on the South Uist radar and on the performance of its new transmitter.

COMPLETED

LJD will report on this in section 5f.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.2 DAH and JDE [Jon Eastment] to develop a business case for replacing the NERC MST Radar's transmitters with modern, solid-state units.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had asked two companies for quotations for replacement equipment. However, he has yet to create a business case.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.3 DAH and JDE [Jon Eastment] to introduce procedures so that someone at RAL will monitor the operation of the MST Radar for periods when DAH is on leave.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that he had considerably expanded the scope of this action. He had created a detailed document of "*Procedures for maintaining NERC MST Radar Facility operations*" covering e.g. how to check if the radar is working, who to inform if it is not, and how to start and stop the radar. CJW confirmed that he had been the one to oversee the radar whilst DAH was on leave in October/November 2014.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.1 GAP to provide DAH with further details of the use of MSTRF data by people who are not registered users.

COMPLETED

GAP will give a report relevant to this in section 3a.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.2 DAH to review security measures for the MST Radar site and to make improvements where necessary.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this had largely been completed, although a few minor improvements are outstanding.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.1 GAP and DAH to remove from the BADC all data files that are known to contain erroneous data.

COMPLETED

GAP and DAH reported that this had been done.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

ONGOING

GAP reported that the BADC is hoping to make use of the CHARMe system, which has already been developed for the purpose of annotating datasets - <http://charme.org.uk/>. He thought that the MSTRF's requirements would be a good test case of the suitability of the system. He and DAH had had

to postpone a meeting to discuss this, but were aiming to reschedule it for the near future.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP gave a short report on how the MSTRF's dataset had been accessed through the BADC during the 2014 calendar year. Prior to 2013, only "registered" users who had submitted a Supporting Scientific Case (now known as an Application for Facility Support) were granted access. The dataset has subsequently become open-access and is now automatically available to everyone with a BADC login. Of the 25 people who had accessed the dataset during 2014, only 2 were registered facility users (there were 9 registered users in total). Although most of the unregistered users had described their discipline as atmospheric science, several were from engineering backgrounds. The quick-look plots and a few other resources have always been open to "public" access, for which no login is required. During 2014, public access was made through 535 unique IP addresses from a range of countries.

GV noted that there are over twice as many unregistered users as registered ones. He asked if there was a way to contact these additional people in order to find out how they were making use of the data. GAP reported the BADC had decided that such contact should be made through them rather than through the instrument scientists responsible for the individual datasets. GV recommended that a similar analysis be carried out on how people are accessing the Chilbolton dataset.

3b) Electricity

Until May 2014, the MSTRF's electricity bills were paid by NERC's Services and Facilities team. NERC have subsequently transferred the responsibility to DAH and provided an "uplift" to the MSTRF's budget to cover this. The electricity supply company are still having difficulties in getting the bills delivered to the correct address. DAH has yet to receive a single one that has not first gone through NERC.

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units indicated brief (~ 1 s) input power problems on 21 occasions during the last 6 months. There were no instances of prolonged problems.

There was a scheduled power outage for the whole of the Capel Dewi area during the daytime of 25th September 2014. DAH only found out about this by chance at 6 pm on the previous evening since he happened to be on site (see section 3d). Although he was scheduled to drive back to RAL on the following morning, he was able warn the Met Office of the outage and to shut down the equipment in a controlled manner before his departure. LD visited the site at the end of the day in order to ensure that everything had powered back up successfully. DAH remotely restarted the MST radar later the same evening.

3c) Telecommunications

The broadband (DrayTek Vigor2830 series ADSL) router that was in operation between June 2011 and January 2014 was prone to occasionally losing its internet connection. It had to be power-cycled in order for normal functioning to be resumed. The router was replaced with a nominally identical, albeit non-wireless, model in March 2014 after the original unit failed. The new unit has not needed to be power-cycled on a single occasion during its 10 months of operation.

EGN reported that she had been having similar drop-out problems at Cardington. Following DAH's recommendation, she had installed the same model of DrayTek router during the previous week. Although it had lost its internet connection on the following day, she suspected that it might not have been configured correctly. It has remained stable since she made some changes to the settings. LD reported

that that MSTRF's connection appears to drop out on a frequent basis, but that the new router is much better at automatically re-establishing it. If he remotely logs on to his site computer from Aberystwyth University, the session usually breaks after some time.

The MSTRF's internet connections, on both the "phone" (University of Manchester) and "fax" (NERC) lines, were slow and/or intermittent between 24th July and 1st August 2014. DAH did not spot this until Monday 28th July, when he noticed a backlog of files that had not been uploaded to RAL. There were gaps of several hours during the evenings of the 24th and the 26th when it appears that no file transfers took place. The problem is thought to have been the result of lightning damage at the Capel Bangor exchange.

The "fax" line was out of action (i.e. no dial tone or internet) between (Friday) 19th and 24th September 2014. When David Wareing (DPW) arrived on site on Monday 22nd, he transferred the NERC router onto the Manchester line. This limited the amount of time for which the Met Office were receiving no real-time data. An Openreach engineer visited the site late in the afternoon of the 24th. He reported that the source of the problem had already been identified elsewhere.

The potential for improving the telecommunications links to the radar site was discussed. GV reported that superfast broadband was being deployed throughout Wales. Although this is supposed to allow download speeds of several tens of megabits per second (Mbps), GV has found that speeds of around 1 Mbps are more likely in the Aberystwyth area. DAH suspected that even if the Capel Bangor exchange were upgraded, the relatively long distance between it and the radar site would remain the limiting factor. GV suggested that 4G, which is not yet available in the Aberystwyth area, might eventually provide an alternative means of connection. However, DAH and LD noted that it was already difficult to pick up a basic mobile phone signal at the radar site owing to its location within a valley.

3d) Miscellaneous

DAH visited the radar site between 23rd and 25th September 2014. This was primarily for the purpose of removing unwanted items. With help from LD, DPW, and John Bradford (from RAL), he managed to fill two skips with approximately one tonne each. He was very pleased with the the service provided by the local Duo Skip hire company - <http://www.duoskip.co.uk/>. They were able to respond to his requests for the delivery and collection of skips at short notice. This meant that he was not held up after unexpectedly filling the first skip within hours of arriving on site.

DAH gave an update on the "chemtrail" conspiracy theory community, who had organised a poorly-attended protest at the MST Radar site in June 2014. Amongst other things, they believe that the radar is being used to control the weather (this belief has subsequently spread to encompass the Met Office's weather radars). Although DAH had initially been concerned by online comments such as "*I am looking for a big bulldozer...to take with me*", he has seen no evidence of any members of this community being involved in violent or destructive direct action. Moreover, their interest in radars is relatively low compared to that in persistent aircraft contrails, which is what they refer to as "chemtrails". Consequently he does not think he needs to adopt a siege mentality so far as the radar site is concerned. Nevertheless, he suspects that there will be a long-lasting, albeit low-level interest in the radar. LD added that a few people had already turned up wanting to see the "Welsh HAARP".

Other members of the science community might occasionally find themselves the unwitting subject of similar interest. Any website that allows member of the public to contribute comments runs the risk of being bombarded with co-ordinated conspiracy postings - e.g. <https://www.facebook.com/bbcbreakfast/photos/a.135265026487644.25430.127439507270196/1015115818502556>. Freedom of Information requests must be dealt with in a formal way, even if they look completely non-sensical - e.g. https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/transmission_wavelengths_weather. A new tactic, which is being used by a small number of the more-active members of the

chemtrail community, is to attend science workshops. They have given presentations and tried to engage with the expected attendees - e.g. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qZ1q-iAjUZ0>. Two such people had tried to invite themselves to the previous MST Experimenters' meeting.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

The Windows PC "Gaius", which acquires data from the Campbell Scientific surface met and surface wind sensors and from the laser ceilometer, developed an error on 27th July 2014. Although this did not halt the data acquisition, it did prevent the files from being automatically transferred to the BADC. It also prevented DAH from logging in remotely. LD cleared the error message when he was on site on the 29th and this resolved the problem.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There is nothing to report in connection with these sensors.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There is nothing to report in connection with these sensors.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

This instrument needs to be replaced. For the period between 17th September and 13th October 2014, although data messages continued to be returned to PC "augustus", the pressure, temperature, and humidity (PTU) fields contained missing datum values. The precipitation and wind data fields appear to have been unaffected. Power-cycling the unit had no effect and normal functioning was eventually resumed without any further intervention having been taken. It was suspected that the combined PTU sensor was at fault. Vaisala recommend that these be replaced every two years although the original one had been in operation for seven years. A new sensor was installed on 18th November after the missing datum problem returned intermittently between 20th and 25th October. Although this was initially successful, the wind data fields started to be populated by missing datum values on 21st December. The unit stopped returning messages of any kind on 31st December. LD later found that the internal electronics showed signs of water damage. After drying the unit out, he returned it to operations on 13th January 2015. However, only the precipitation sensor is continuing to return actual data. The WXT510 was discontinued by Vaisala in 2008 and so it will be replaced with a WXT520.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The data acquisition software, which runs on Windows PC "gaius", stopped working during the early hours of 24th July 2014. DAH spotted this later the same morning and restarted the program.

4e) Sky-camera

A new camera was installed on 1st December 2014. The original camera failed in September 2013, but could not be easily accessed owing to the fact that it was 4 m above the ground and fenced in behind the instrument compound. The new camera - an Axis M1113 - was installed by Dyfed Alarms, who are used to installing cameras in diverse locations. The new camera has been installed slightly to the right of the old one and has been aligned so that its field of view is as similar as possible. However, the upper-left hand side of the image is slightly obscured by the side of the building. DAH is delaying the routine acquisition of images until he has defined the metadata, which will be embedded in the image files.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

The NLC camera was operated between 1st June and 4th August 2014. It captured NLCs on a several nights. It also managed to capture images of lightning during the early hours of 18th July 2014.

4g) MST Radar

LJD began by presenting the recent EUMETNET Composite Observing System (EUCOS) data quality statistics. The daily number of observations (i.e. the cumulative sum of the number of range gates containing valid data across all profiles for the day) underwent a step increase of approximately 10% in June 2014. The reason for this is not known. The number of observations was very low or zero on several days. Some of these gaps could be explained, e.g. by radar downtime (25th September 2014) and by internet problems (19th - 22nd September 2014). However, there was no apparent reason for the lack of observations between 30th October and 3rd November 2014. The daily values of the root mean square differences between radar and model wind speeds for the last six months were predominantly within the EUCOS target range. The direction differences were more likely to exceed the target values. Nevertheless, the data quality overall was deemed to be good.

The Met Office's model comparison statistics have switched from using the global model to the much-higher-resolution UKV model. These statistics show good agreement for all wind parameters and no significant changes since the previous reporting period. GV commented on the fact that the Met Office's statistics have always shown a slight positive speed bias for radar data in the troposphere and a slight negative one in the stratosphere. He pointed out that Chris Lee's recent paper - <http://www.atmos-meas-tech.net/7/3113/2014/amt-7-3113-2014.html> - showed a similar pattern in radar-radiosonde comparisons. He had attributed this to the horizontal separation between the radar and radiosonde measurements, which meant that they were observing different phases of ubiquitous mountain waves.

LJD went on to give a report of the performance of the Met Office's South Uist radar following its May 2014 renovation (i.e. action item 53.2.1). The radar was originally supplied by Vaisala, albeit making use of some ATRAD hardware. The renovated system now relies exclusively on ATRAD hardware and software - <http://www.atrad.com.au/special-projects/vaisala-lap12000-upgrade/>. LJD presented model-comparison statistics for November 2013 and for November 2014. These indicate a large increase in useful data coverage. As well as the expected improvement at the higher altitudes, the minimum observable altitude is now approximately 1 km lower than it used to be. The emergency power generator has now been decommissioned and the radar system has been configured to automatically restart as soon as power resumes following an outage. Finally, LJD showed an instance of unexpected radar returns from the 20 - 100 km altitude range and wondered if this could be the effect of space weather. DAH reported that he had spoken to Mike Prots (Met Office) about such an occurrence. He (DAH) was of the opinion this and that this was the result of some sort of internal interference.

DAH presented the rest of this section on the Aberystwyth MST radar. The transmitter for antenna sector B (TXB) was out of action owing to a blown fuse for 5 hours on 20th July 2014 and for 4 days starting on 22nd August. It was out of action between 30th September and 7th October owing to the fact that it could not be kept in stable operation. LD changed the PIN diodes and the voltage regulator before bringing it back into operation.

TXC was out of action owing to a blown fuse for 2 days starting on 27th July 2014 and for 4 hours on 23rd December. It shut down with an analogue error on 5 occasions: for 22 hours starting on 10th July, for 3 days starting on 15th November, for 9 hours starting on 21st November, and for 3 days starting on 27th December.

TXE was out of action with a blown fuse for approximately 8 hours on the morning of 4th November 2014.

During the four days following the scheduled power outage on 25th September 2014, there were several transmitter problems. This resulted in noticeably reduced altitude coverage. TXB blew its fuse and TXD developed an analogue error shortly after they were switched back on on the 25th. TXE blew its fuse a

few hours later. Although DAH managed to remotely restart TXD on the morning of the 26th, it shut down again almost immediately. This happened several more times in short succession. All transmitters came back into operation on morning of the 29th.

The radar was stopped for approximately 45 minutes on the morning of 30th September 2014. This was to allow LD to change beam steering unit 94, which had been reporting slightly elevated Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) values. Late in the evening of 1st November, the beam steering controller gave a series of unusual warning and error messages indicating a segmentation fault and process failures. This coincided with the duration of the 23:11:14 UT observation cycle being 40 s longer than usual. Normal operation appears to have resumed during the subsequent cycle. The radar was stopped for approximately 30 minutes on 30th December 2014. This was to allow LD to change beam steering unit 15, which had intermittently been reporting a low supply voltage.

The radar has suffered from a raised noise floor or interference on a number of occasions. An instance lasting for approximately one hour on 19th August 2014 appeared to only affect the mesospheric observations. Another instance lasting for approximately one hour on 29th September led to reduced altitude coverage for the wind-profile data. The problem was seen more persistently between 5th and 8th January 2015.

5. Guest Instrument Report

DAH gave a report on the Met Office's Global Positioning System (GPS) water vapour receiver on behalf of Jon Jones, who was not at the meeting. The old Ashtec receiver, which could only make use of signals from the American GPS satellites, has been replaced with a Leica GR10 GNSS receiver, which can additionally make use signals from the Russian Glosnass and European Galileo satellites. The processing system at the Met Office is due to be upgraded so that it can make use of the additional data. Jon plans to replace the Aberystwyth antenna and to install a UPS unit for the receiver. The latter is needed owing to the fact that the electricity supply at the radar site is prone to irregularities. The MSTRF's UPS units are located too far away from the receiver to be easily accessible.

The MSTRF has been hosting a LINET lightning detector system for the commercial company nowcast since early 2011. Nowcast have informed DAH that the Aberystwyth system is contaminated with a very high noise level, which makes the data unusable. DAH and LD have been unable to identify a potential cause.

HMAR reported on the lidars. A recent summer student worked on software for the analysis of volcanic ash observations. This software can now be used to analyse data from both lidar systems. The Elight lidar has been suffering from heating and cooling problems, but is now almost back in working order. It has not been involved in any field campaigns recently. It is hoped to upgrade it to include a photon counting capability. This would allow it to be operated in Raman mode.

GV reported on the Système d'Analyse par Observation Zénithale (SAOZ) instrument, which measures ozone and nitrogen dioxide column amounts. It is a diode array spectrometer, which covers the ultraviolet to visible range of 300 - 650 nm. Until 2010, the data used to be processed manually using the WinDOAS software. The new, automated QDOAS software is much easier to use. Nitrogen dioxide amounts derived from the two sets of software are in very close agreement. Although ozone amounts are generally in good agreement, GV is still trying to understand the reason for differences. The instrument began operations in 1991 in connection with the Arctic ozone programme. Although there have been no funds to support it since GV's move to Manchester, it is robust, reliable, and requires little attention. Moreover, there is ongoing interest in long-term trends in stratospheric ozone. This requires a worldwide network of well-characterised, long-term datasets. The UK government has an obligation to support this through the 1985 Vienna Convention. One of the advantages of the SAOZ instrument is

its relatively low cost.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Improving Theta S/Theta Effective Correction - DAH

This presentation concerned the zenith angle dependence of MST radar backscatter, which is also known as the aspect sensitivity. Before going into the details of his recent analyses, DAH explained the significance of this phenomenon for turbulence studies - see next presentation. The zenith angle dependence is determined by the shape of the refractive index irregularities that cause the backscatter. Where turbulent mixing occurs, the refractive index irregularities are expected to be isotropic and the zenith angle dependence to be small. However, it's not clear for how long the irregularities remain isotropic after the mixing has ceased or by what mechanism they become anisotropic. Consequently a small zenith angle dependence cannot necessarily be interpreted as indicating the presence of active turbulence for the troposphere, where the dependence is predominantly small. Nevertheless, it appears to be a reliable indicator in the stratosphere, where the dependence is predominantly large - see e.g. Hooper and Thomas (1998), <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364682697000540>. A large zenith angle dependence at any altitude unambiguously indicates an absence of volume-filling turbulence.

DAH then focused on his work relating to action item 51.6.1. Where the zenith angle dependence is large, the effective zenith angle of an off-vertical beam will be slightly smaller than the nominal angle. A correction factor must be applied to the wind speed in order to compensate for this - see e.g. Thomas et al. (1997), <http://www.ann-geophys.net/15/805/1997/angeo-15-805-1997.html>, and the Lee et al. (2014) paper referenced in section 4g. The correction factor is currently based on single cycle values of signal power for observations made at two zenith angles: at 6.0° , for which an average is taken from the NE6.0, SE6.0, SW6.0, and NW6.0 beams, and at 4.2° , for which just the W4.2 beam is used. DAH had previously demonstrated that this factor is adding random error to the wind speed estimates. However, he had also found that the underlying single cycle estimates of the wind vector are noisy and that they should be averaged over at least 6 cycles/30 minutes.

DAH is now considering whether the current choice of beam pointing directions for calculating the correction factor is entirely appropriate. Even after 30 minute averaging, the spread between signal powers for the four 6.0° off-vertical beams can be greater than 5 dB. DAH was surprised that there could be so much azimuthal variation even where the zenith angle dependence is small. This result suggests that the signal powers at 4.2° off-vertical should be based on the average from all four available azimuths. However, this would significantly increase the cycle duration for comparatively little gain. An alternative approach might be to base the wind speed correction factor on a comparison of signal powers for zenith angles of 0.0° and 6.0° . Although previous work suggests that this would lead to an overestimate of the correction factor, it might be possible to take this into account. DAH aims to evaluate this possibility using the observations made in all 17 available beam pointing directions during the post-renovation period of March and April 2011.

GV highlighted the fact that the purpose of this correction factor is to reduce the systematic error in wind speeds. It should not do this at the expense of increasing the random error. Moreover, he stressed that DAH needs to demonstrate that using dynamically-calculated values is better than using fixed climatological values.

6b) Measuring turbulence with adapted radiosondes and comparison with MST radar - GM

Clear air turbulence remains a hazard for the airline industry owing to the limited skill of the forecast tools currently available. The scope for improving these tools is restricted by the lack of instruments that can routinely detect turbulence. Consequently a central aspect of GM's PhD project, which is aimed at improving the understanding of turbulence, is to build up a dataset of measurements taken under di-

verse meteorological conditions. He is using standard RS92 radiosondes that have been adapted to carry a three-axis accelerometer. The two are interfaced through the Programmable ANalogue and Digital Operational Radiosonde Accessory (PANDORA) package, which has been developed at Reading University. Changes in the balloons speed or direction will agitate the sonde and cause it to swing. The amplitude of the swings will increase as the variations in balloon motion become larger and more frequent. GM showed data from a flight that encountered moderate turbulence within frontal cloud and intense turbulence within the core of the jet. In the latter case, peak accelerations of $6g$ were detected. GV and DAH pointed out that a region of increased static stability and of low humidity appeared to correspond to a tropopause fold. The intensity of turbulence within this region was small.

GM has already found a reasonable correlation between radiosonde and (Halo Photonics) Doppler lidar measurements of turbulence within the boundary layer. For the lidar data, the eddy dissipation rate is derived from a $-5/3$ fit to the spectrum of vertical velocity fluctuations within a 30 minute window surrounding the launch time of the radiosonde (it is also possible to use the standard deviation of the fluctuations). The equivalent radiosonde parameter is the standard deviation in the z-axis (i.e. along the direction of the string connecting the radiosonde to the balloon) accelerometer readings over a 210 m altitude window.

GM has begun to look at MST Radar data as a way of extending comparisons to altitudes above the boundary layer. He already launched 5 radiosondes from the radar site on 13th and 14th January 2015. On both days the jet stream was overhead with peak speeds $50 - 60 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. GM presented data from just one of these launches. They show turbulent activity throughout the troposphere. The corresponding MST radar data show low aspect sensitivity and at least moderate values of the beam-broadening corrected spectral width ($0.1 - 0.7 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) within the same altitude region. DAH was particularly interested in what appeared, from the radiosonde data, to be two thin layers of turbulence in the lower stratosphere. Their discrete nature makes them good subjects for comparisons between the radar and radiosonde techniques. GM plans to conduct more radiosonde launches and hopes to capture mountain wave breaking conditions. GV and HMAR thought that it should be possible to extend the loan of the radiosonde equipment beyond the current end date of late February.

6c) NCAS-AMF Mobile Radar Wind Profiler - EGN

EGN drew attention to the new official name - NCAS-AMF Mobile Radar Wind Profiler - for the boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP). It is currently in operation at the Met Office's Cardington site, for which it has built up a longer dataset than for any other site. EGN recently renewed the Ofcom non-operational development license for use of the BLWP at the site. Although the instrument has been operating well, broadband and router problems have affected data transfers - see section 3f. Wind data are being sent to the Met Office without being assimilated. The model-comparison statistics all fall within the EUCOS targets for acceptability, although the systematic differences are larger than those for the MST radar. Wind speeds are on average 2 m s^{-1} below radiosonde values. GV pointed out that Chris Lee had looked into this issue in detail. He had found that the wind speeds also showed a negative bias with respect to those from the MST radar. He thought it was something to do with vertical velocities.

The Cardington clutter screen suffered damage from storms in early January 2014. This is thought to have been the cause for increased clutter seen in the spectra. Funds are available for the screen to be rebuilt. The antennas are suffered from a buildup of algae. These were cleaned and the manufacturer (Degreane) suggested spraying them with a dilute solution of bicarbonate of soda in order to slow down regrowth.

The data acquisition computer (PCA) had suffered from FIFO overflow messages at the start of the COPE campaign in 2013. These would stop the radar from working and required PCA to be manually rebooted. The problem had ceased when the software was upgraded and the calculation of spectra was transferred back to the digital signal processing board. However, it has recently recurred on an intermit-

tent basis.

The data processing computer (PCT) was replaced during 2014. It runs a RAID server and has already had to have two hard drives replaced. Moreover, the switch to Windows 7 has caused a number of problems. The PCT software was upgraded to version 6.45 in December 2014. Owing to the various problems, EGN has switched back to using the older PCT.

The averaging period for data has been changed to 30 minutes with an update every 15 minutes. This was used until 2011, when the Met Office requested that it be changed to 15 minute averaging with an update every 15 minutes. However, if the winds show too little variation during the averaging period, they are rejected since it is assumed that they must represent clutter or interference - hence the change back to 30 minutes. Upgrades to PCA are planned for May 2015. It will use 18 bit analogue to digital converter, which will allow an additional 24 dB of dynamic range.

Hourly updated plots of the latest profiler data are now available through a link on the NCAS website - <https://www.ncas.ac.uk/index.php/en/live-data>. There is also a new CEDA catalogue page for this instrument - <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/6677116482304866b881a0028af44eee> - which connects to all of the BLWP's dataset catalogue pages, which link to the data in the BADC archives. GAP reported that the search capability of the catalogue pages has been improved. However, EGN said that she found it difficult to understand the results. She also thought it would be useful to include links to the quick-look data plots. GM added that some of the names of the "Datasets" on the MSTRF's catalogue page - <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/bd095d86e4a9f0c706b08058dbad3b31> - were ambiguous owing to the fact that they had been truncated. They were shown as "Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere...", with no indication of what differentiated them. GAP invited people to continue feeding back comments/complaints/suggestions to him so that issues feed through to the developers and dataset managers.

EGN reported that changes had been made to IDL code routines for reading profiler data. These were needed to keep up with the small changes that Degreane make to the binary file formats when they upgrade the software. GAP pointed that these changes need to be documented.

EGN reported that funding was in place for the purchase of a ceilometer. The aim is integrate it with the BLWP, i.e. to mount it on the same trailer and to include the cloud base data in the DAT files produced by PCA. This will allow both sets of data to be viewed simultaneously in real time. EGN is still in the process of deciding which model of ceilometer to purchase. She had already spoken to Judith Agnew, who has experience of both Vaisala and Campbell Scientific instruments.

6d) Assimilation of wind profiler data - CG

CG gave a short verbal update on her current work with ZL. They are trying to establish whether wind-profiler signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) values could be usefully assimilated for the purposes of numerical weather prediction. Range-squared-corrected S/N is typically assumed to depend on the vertical gradient of generalised potential refractive index, which is denoted by M . The values are derived from the model fields of temperature and humidity. However, CG found that this parameter did not show sufficient structure and so she has been looking at the vertical gradient of regular refractive index instead. In some cases this has shown a reasonable agreement with the radar data in the high-altitude-coverage mode. However, the high-altitude-resolution radar data shows much more structure than the model data.

In order to continue with this line of enquiry, it will be necessary to develop a precipitation flag. The standard clear air scattering model ceases to be valid under precipitation conditions. It would also help to know more about the profiler manufacturer's signal processing software. For example, the atmospheric

signal parameters could be affected by the way in which it deals with interference.

7. Any Other Business

EGN was interested in the possibility of attaching an accelerometer, together with a camera, to a radiosonde for public engagement activities. HMAR was also interested from a Royal Meteorological Society perspective. GM pointed out that, at Reading, they had experience of attaching a range of devices to modified radiosondes.

The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for 28th June 2015 (it was later fixed for Thursday 2nd July). There was a reminder that the NCAS science meeting was taking place on 16th and 17th July in York.